

Drought resistance

Root growth and water extraction pattern of six rices in rainfed conditions

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In 1983 kharif we studied root growth and water extraction pattern of six rices grown in upland rainfed fields. Vertical rooting distributions of the varieties differed (Fig. 1).

Safri 17 had the highest root density (57 mg/cm³) in the top 10 cm of soil, and MW10 had the lowest (19 mg/cm³). Mahsuri, Usha, IR36, and Poorva were similar with intermediate density. Eighty-nine to 94% of roots were in the top 10 cm of soil, 4 to 9% were in the 10 to 20 cm layer, and the rest were 20 to 50 cm deep.

Figure 2 shows the water absorption patterns from flowering to maturity for Safri 17, Mahsuri, and Usha. The other varieties matured before rains ceased, preventing the study of their water extraction patterns.

Varietal differences in water extraction paralleled those of root growth. Root density in the 0 to 10 cm layer was highest for Safri 17, as was water extraction, which increased gradually with increasing depth to 45 cm – lowest depth measurement.

Five days after rains ceased, water extraction from the 5 to 45 cm soil layer was 1.6 mm/d for Safri 17, 0.8 for Mahsuri, and 0.8 for Usha. During the next 20 d, water extraction from the 5 to 15 cm layer diminished considerably, and extraction from 35 to 45 cm increased markedly.

A comparison of water extraction pattern (Fig. 2) and rooting pattern (Fig. 1) suggests that rooting density might not have been the sole determinant of water uptake. Soil water factors (soil water pressure and potential, and hydraulic conductivity) must also be considered. Five days after rains ceased, soil water

2. Water extraction pattern of 3 rice varieties, Raipur, India.

factors favored water uptake from the surface layers. Twenty days later, when surface soil had dried, the crops extracted water from the deeper, wetter layers. Figure 2 shows that rice varieties differ

in their ability to extract water from the deeper layers. Those differences can be exploited by choosing appropriate varieties for drought-prone upland environments. □

Deep water

Germination of seed from deep water varieties grown in deep water and field conditions

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Photoperiod-sensitive floating rices Jaladhi 1 and Jaladhi 2 were grown in

deep water and normal field conditions at the Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal. Weekly water level variations in two plots are in Figure 1.

The seeds were direct-seeded in wet soil (37-41% soil moisture) in late May. At harvest (Dec), the field had 25-30% soil moisture and the deep water plot had about 40 cm water. Seeds were thoroughly dried, cleaned, and stored in cloth bags.